

Availability of Players is Associated with Success in Soccer

Jinying Jiang¹, Daniel Link^{1,2}

June 2026

PREPRINT - THIS PAPER WAS NOT PEER REVIEWED

Abstract

Availability in soccer refers to the probability that a selected player can successfully receive a pass from a teammate. This study explores how performance indicators derived from Availability (AV) are connected to success in soccer. Therefore, we used spatiotemporal tracking data of 47 German Bundesliga matches, containing 45,332 passes. Availability was calculated for each moment that a player has individual ball possession and for all players of his team. The quantification is based on a mixture of physical models and machine learning algorithms. Results show that passing success rate is significantly correlated ($r=.3$) with Availability of the receiver. Also, Availability was significantly ($p < .05$, $d = 0.14$) higher on successful passes ($AV=.84$) compared to situation in which the ball carrier loses the ball ($AV=.59$). Analysis of turnovers revealed that number of Players Available (PA) was significantly higher ($p < .05$, $d = 0.68$) in successful turnovers ($PA=4.7$) compared to turnovers with direct ball loss ($PA=3.9$). In addition, the team's average longitudinal space gain following a turnover is associated with the number of Players Available. For example, mean space gain after 5 seconds was 5.9 m when only one teammate was available, compared to 10.9 m when three teammates were available ($p < .05$, $r=0.3$). We conclude that Availability is associated with success on sub-aim level in soccer. These results provide an empirical justification to use Availability for match analysis.

Keywords: Availability; xPass; Turnover; Spatiotemporal tracking data; Passing success; performance indicator

Cite preliminary as: Jiang, J. & Link, D. (2026). Availability of Players is Associated with Success in Soccer. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20633636>.

¹Technical University Munich, Experimental Exercise Science, Munich, Germany. TUM Campus at Olympia-park. Tel. +49 (0) 89/289 24501, Technical University Munich, 80992 Munich. Germany, T: +49.89.289.24498, E: jinying.jiang@tum.de

²Technical University Munich, Munich Data Science Institute, Munich, Germany

Introduction

Passes are the most frequent actions in soccer (Pappalardo et al., 2019). By circulating the ball among teammates, teams aim to locate low-pressure spaces in order to keep possession after turnovers or to move closer to the opponent's goal. More aggressive, penetrative passes attempt to bypass defensive lines and create goal-scoring opportunities. Consequently, passing quality plays a crucial role in team success and serves as a key measure for evaluating both collective and individual performance (Hughes & Franks, 2005). At the same time, simple performance indicators (PI) such as pass completion rate offer only limited insight into a player's true passing ability (Mackenzie & Cushion, 2013). Therefore, research emphasizes the importance of more sophisticated metrics that take into account the context of each pass, as well as the balance between its associated risk and potential reward (Goes et al., 2018; Lotte et al., 2019; Memmert, 2025; Overmeer, Janssen, & Nuijten, 2025; Power et al., 2017).

A promising concept for evaluating passing performance is *Availability*, defined as the probability that a selected player can successfully receive a pass from a teammate (Dick, Link, & Brefeld, 2022). Although Availability is closely related to the risk of a pass, it is not equivalent to xPass (Anzer & Bauer, 2022), as it does not describe a single, specific action. Rather, it captures the overall likelihood that one of several potential passes, directed toward advantageous areas on the field, can be completed successfully. From a practical perspective, performance indicators (PIs) based on Availability appear highly relevant for performance analysis. For the player in possession, passing involves choosing between multiple potential targets while simultaneously controlling the ball's direction and speed in accordance with the movement of the intended receiver. In this situation, the Availability of teammates becomes a key factor for evaluating both decision-making quality and technical execution. At the same time, Availability is equally important for assessing the tactical behavior of off-ball players. If teammates fail to move into open spaces, passing options are reduced, increasing the likelihood of interceptions by the opposing team. However, from a scientific perspective, it is not sufficient to rely solely on the intuitive or face validity of Availability-based PIs. Instead, empirical validity is required to determine their actual explanatory value for soccer performance, which being the central aim of the present study.

In recent decades, the validity of PIs has been widely debated in sports science. Hughes and Bartlett (2002) argued that PIs should reflect meaningful aspects of performance and can be regarded as useful and valid when they are linked to success. O'Donoghue (2009) outlined specific criteria, stating that a variable can only be considered a PI if it fulfills three measurement-related requirements: it must be based on an objective measurement procedure, rely on a clearly defined scale, and allow for transparent and sound interpretation. Lames and McGarry (2007) emphasized the importance of consistency in measurement, highlighting reliability as a key prerequisite that can be evaluated through standard procedures such as intra- and inter-rater agreement. Mackenzie et al. (2013) expanded this perspective by stressing the need to consider the contextual conditions under which PIs are applied. Franks and Hughes (2016) proposed additional criteria to ensure the practical relevance of PIs, including their ability to discriminate effectively between players or teams. More recently,

Morgulev and Lebed (2024) offered a comprehensive critique of existing PI research, identifying key challenges such as the influence of confounding variables. Davis et al. (2024) further examined methodological considerations and evaluation approaches, particularly in the context of machine learning based performance indicators. They also propose a face validity test, meaning that a PI should reflect conventional wisdom about the performance of individuals and teams.

Maybe the most crucial aspect of a PI in soccer is its relation to success. The ultimate objective is to score one more goal than the opposing team and thereby win the match. However, soccer is a low-scoring game, meaning goals occur relatively infrequently and are therefore not very useful for describing team performance within a single match. Against this backdrop, research suggests decomposing success into more specific objectives, such as effective defensive play, restricting the opponent's build-up, controlling space, winning the second ball after goal kicks and reaching the final third (Baca & Perl, 2018; Memmert & Perl, 2009). Based on these sub-aims, more frequently occurring proxy variables can be defined to predict the less frequent, decisive outcome variable. If a metric reliably captures these sub-aspects of performance, it can be considered a PI for that specific soccer domain. In summary, Lang (2026) defined the validity of performance indicators in terms of three key aspects: 1) measurement quality, 2) substantive validity and 3) practical usefulness. Measurement quality addresses the overall soundness and reliability of the data on which PIs are based. Substantive validity refers to the relationships between indicators, theoretical constructs and success-related outcomes. Practical usefulness refers to the extent to which the indicators are interpretable, feasible, novel and genuinely helpful for decision-making in practice.

Against this background, the present study is the first one extensively evaluating the concept of Availability in soccer. It adopts the Availability metric developed by Dick et al. (2022) as a foundation for exploring its validity and applicability as a tactical performance indicator. Whereas measurement quality (1) was evaluated in the first publication, this paper focuses on substantive validity (2) and practical usefulness (3). We organized our paper along with three research questions. Firstly, we provide the prevalence of Availability in professional matches (Question i). This provides a face-validity test, since there are reasonable expectations of how Availability should behave following conventional wisdom in soccer. Here, we explore different ways on how to calculate the numbers of players available from the raw value and show how Availability depends on the position of passer and potential receiver. Secondly, we test how Availability is related to success (Question ii). According to the discussion above, we look at more granulated criteria for success using sub-aims. Therefore, we first ask whether Availability of teammates differs in situations in which ball possession was lost versus ball possession was retained. Secondly, we look at the specific situation of a turn-over, where a player gained individual ball possession by successfully tackling the opponent or intercepting a pass. For these situations we asked whether Availability affects a) the probability to establish "stable" team ball possession and b) the extent of space gain after the turn-over. Thirdly, we show how Availability can be used for performance analysis in practice (Question iii). For one specific match we ask how

availability of players evolves after turnovers and discuss how this information can be used for decision-making on team level in practice. We also show Availability can be used to create meaningful passing profiles on an individual level. Addressing these questions advances our understanding of Availability in soccer and provides a justification to use it as a Performance Indicator for match analysis.

Methods

Data sample

In line with the objectives of the study, a retrospective, non-participative observational approach was applied. Sample comprises 47 matches of 2017/18 German Bundesliga season. Spatial-temporal data of players and ball was collected with 25 Hz by multi-camera tracking system TRACAB Gen5 of Chyron Hego. Event data was collected by professional human observers. Accuracy, validity, and reliability of data have been confirmed by previous studies (Linke, Link, & Lames, 2020). Since each player agreed to data recording of matches on signing their player license, special approval for this study from an ethics committee was not required. Nevertheless, all procedures performed in the study were in strict accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki as well as with the ethical standards of the local ethics committee.

Performance Variables

Based on the raw data, we derived a set of observational units and PIs (Table 1). Availability represents the probability of a player receiving the ball from a teammate. It is calculated for each moment that a player has individual ball possession and for all players of his team. The quantification bases on a mixture of physical models and machine learning algorithms, which is explained in detail by Dick et al. (2022). The method considers that (i) players are constantly in motion and may receive the ball at many different positions on the pitch, (ii) there are many possible trajectories and passing speeds of the ball to the same position resulting in different transition times of the ball, (iii) opponents may intercept the ball, (iv) the technical skill levels of pass giver and the (v) time for controlling esp. high passes influence successful completion of the pass. For every moment t , we compute probabilities at which player r can receive a pass at the position x . After this, we aggregate those probabilities for many x to an overall probability of a successful pass, which we call Availability of r at the moment t (Figure 1). Reliability of Availability calculation was evaluated in multiplied ways including a comparison with ratings of human observers (Dick et al., 2022). Correlations between expert rating and our calculation was $r=.7$ which is in the range of correlation between to independent human observers.

Table 1. Observational units and performance indicators

Observation Units

Individual Ball Possession (IBP)	IBP refers to the timespan a player has possession of the ball according to the method proposed by Link and Hoernig (2017). We only use IBPs in which the player carries the ball and passes at the end of the IBP by foot or loses ball possession in a ground duel. Other actions such as Clearances or Attempts at Goal were excluded.
Pass	Pass is an IBP that ends with attempting to move ball possession to a teammate. The ball must travel at least one meter.
Turnover	Turnover is an IBP in which a player wins ball possession for the own team. We only considered Turnovers in which the team losing ball possession had established team possession before (no ping-pong situations), and the player winning ball possession fulfills a set of criteria (field player, was able to establish ball control, no one-touch, no header, no foul, no set play).

Performance Indicators

Availability (AV)	Availability to the probability a player can receive a Pass from teammate, which is time continuous variable, available for each moment of an IBP.
Possession Retained	For IBP, Possession Retained is true when the player was able to transfer the ball to a teammate by passing. Otherwise, e.g. the pass is intercepted, out of play, or the player lost a duel while carrying the ball, Possession retained is false.
Receiver Availability	For IBP, Receiver Availability refers to AV of a teammate at the end of the IBA (the moment in which the passer touches the ball). We differentiated between three situations: First, if Possession is Retained, Receiver Availability refers to AV of the receiver. Second, if Possession is not Retained and IBP ended with a pass, this refers to AV of the intended receiver. Intended receiver was estimated by using a geometrical model including the receiver distance to the passing line and the distance of potential receivers to the passer in relation to the ball speed, with the potential receiver identified as the nearest player within one meter, or within ten meters at the ball's first land. Third, if Possession is not Retained and IBP ended by losing the ball in a duel, this refers to maximum AV of all teammates.
Players Available	For IBP, Players Available represent the number of players available at the end of an IBP. Since AV is metric, we first calculated a dichotomic representation by applying a Threshold of $>.8$ to define a teammate as available.
Space Gain	For Turnover, Space gain represents the difference of the ball distance to the opponents' goal line in the moment of the turnover and the distance of the ball to the goal-line 5 seconds later (in m). It is only valid for turnovers, where the team still had ball possession after 5 seconds after turnover.

Figure 1. Principles of Availability quantification. Availability bases on a mixture of physical models and machine learning algorithms, which is explained in detail by Dick et al. (2022). Interception Time is determined based on a movement model based on current velocity vector (Dick et al., 2022). Reception difficulty considers that high passes are much more difficult to control. The illustration at the bottom shows possible ball reception zones (red) for each teammate and the probability score.

Our data also contains a set of qualifiers associated with each observational unit. This includes start and ending timestamp, identity of player and the player position. For each player there is a qualifier Forward Player that indicates whether a player out of ball possession is closer to the opponent goal line compared to the teammate in ball possession. Particularly, if a teammate is closer 16m from the opponent’s goal line, we also considered teammates closer to the horizontal center line of the pitch as Forward Players, even if their distance to the goal line was greater.

Statistical Analysis

For exploring prevalence of Availability (Question i), we apply four different kinds of visualization. Fig. 2a takes IBP as the statistical unit and shows Players Available according to the three conditions Threshold, Direction and Time by using Ridge plots. Thresholds refers to threshold used to define a teammate as available ($> .7, .8$ or $.9$). Direction specifies the players to include; the category All comprises all teammates on the pitch, Forward includes the Forward Players only. Category Time refers to the way PA is attributed to an IBP. Since PA exists for all moments inside an IBP, there are degrees of freedom to do this. Category Max uses the maximum AV for a player during an IBP; category End uses AV at the end of an IBP.

Analysis of spatial dependency of Availability uses Pass x Teammate as statistical unit and visualize AV of teammates by their absolute position on the pitch (Figure 2b) as well as by their relative position to the last second player (Offside Line Distance (m)) (see Figure 2c). For both, we use the ISOPAR method proposed by Stöckl, Lamb, and Lames (2012). For showing Availability according to the relative position of passer and potential receiver, AV is plotted according to the Passing Distance (distance between

passer and potential receiver) and the angle α relative to the goal direction (see Figure 2d). The angle α is defined as the angle between the straight line connecting the passer and teammates and the line from the passer to the center of the goal. A pass directed straight toward the goal corresponds to $\alpha=0$. Figure 2b and 2c use Direction category Forward, whereas Figure 2d use category All. All of these Figures use Time category End.

To evaluate the relation of Availability to success (Question ii), four approaches are applied. First, we use Pass as statistical unit and assigned them to 10 groups by using Availability ([0-0.1], [0.1-0.2], ..., [0.9-1.0]). For analyzing relationship between Possession Retained Rate and Availability Group, linear regression model is used (Figure 3a). Secondly, we use IBP as statistical unit and group them by Possession Retained. Difference in Receiver Availability between Possession Retained Groups are shown by a boxplot (Figure 3b). Thirdly, analysis uses Turnover as statistical unit and grouped them by Possession Retained. We use boxplot for reporting the distribution of Players Available per Possession Retained Group (Figure 3c). Fourthly, Turnovers where we grouped by Players Available. Boxplot shows the distribution of Space Gain per Players Available Group (Figure 3d). Kruskal-Wallis's test, Man-Whitney U-tests and t-tests were carried out to analyze differences between groups. Preconditions for applying parameter tests were verified. Effect size d was calculated according to Cohen. Alpha level was set to 0.05. Python 3.9 were utilized as the primary statistical and computational tool.

To give an example on how Availability can be used in practice (Question iii). On team level we show an illustration of Availability and Players Available evolvement after one selected turnover (Figure 4a). Afterwards we characterize two teams based on Players Available evolvement after turnovers in 3 matches. Therefore, we grouped turnovers into three Players Available Groups (0, 1, >1) and report the evolution of group sizes after 1, 2 and 3 seconds after the turnover (Figure 4b). On player level, we report a "Passing Risk-Profile" (Figure 4c). For this we selected all players with more than 100 passes. For each player, we grouped passes by Receiver Availability in 10 groups and calculated the Individual Passing Frequency (%) (number of Passes per group divided by total number of passes) per group. For an individual player, the indicator Percentile refers to the percentile of his Individual Passing Frequency in the entire sample of players for one Receiver Availability Group. In the same way we create a "Risk-Success-Profile", by not using Individual Passing Frequency but Individual Possession Retained Rate (%) per group (Figure 4d).

Results

Our dataset contains 60,154 IBPs and 44,276 passes were played. 41,017 passes were classified as successful, and 3,259 passes as unsuccessful. Besides, there are 1,842 turnovers in 47 matches, of which 1,579 were classified as successful turnover, and 263 as unsuccessful turnover.

Question i: Prevalence of Pass Availability

Figure 2a presents the distribution of Players Available per IBA in different Configurations. With increasing Threshold, the number of Players Available dropped

notably, from a mean of around 6.9 players ($AV > .7$) to fewer than 1.1 players ($AV > .9$). When considering Forward Players only, number of Players Available was consistently lower, typically by about 2.5 players by mean. Furthermore, player availability increased around 1.4 players when using Max AV for a player during an IBP instead of using AV at the End.

Figure 2b displays the spatial distribution of player availability across the pitch ($n=242,464$). Average AV in the defensive and middle thirds ranged between .5 and .7, while in the attacking third, especially in central zones close to the penalty area that AV dropped below .3. The flanks maintained relatively higher AV values ($\sim .4-.6$).

Figure 2c illustrates the relationship between player availability and proximity to the opponent's 'offside line'. As attackers advance toward the final defensive line, AV values decline gradually from approximately .5 in deeper positions to below .2 near the offside line, reflecting the spatial compression typical in advanced attacking areas. For example, statistical tests verify that mean AV of receiver with a distance d of $0 < d < 8$ m was 29% below of receivers with a distance of $d > 8$ m.

Figure 2d shows that within the 45° forward-facing field of view of the passer, average AV were the lowest (around .25-.35), whereas lateral and backward directions exhibited higher values (up to .6). For example, Forward Player Availability of Straight ($0^\circ < |a| < 22.5^\circ$) is $.26 \pm 0.23$, which is significant lower ($F=15.6$, $p < .05$, $d = 0.23$) compared to $.7 \pm 0.12$ for sideward players ($67.5^\circ < |a| < 112.5^\circ$). The availability of potential receivers located far from the passer (Player Distance > 30 m) is 19% lower compared to those positioned close to the passer (Player Distance < 10 m) ($F=25.4$, $p < .05$, $d = 0.42$).

Figure 2. Prevalence and spatial dependency of Availability. Higher availability thresholds and forward-direction constraints reduce available players (a). Availability is highest in wide areas but drops below .3 in central attacking zones (b). and declines progressively near the offside line (c). Forward-facing passing options are significantly more constrained than lateral or backward directions (d).

Question ii: Relation of Availability and Success

Figure 3a shows data of all passes performed ($n=45,332$) and illustrates the relationship between receivers AV and the outcome of a pass. Results indicate that higher PA values are associated with a greater percentage of possession retained passes. Correlation analysis further indicated a positive relationship between these passes and players' AV ($t = 2,707.6$, $p < .05$, $d = 0.14$). Figure 3b takes a slightly different perspective and compares IBPs (not only passes), where a player lost the ball ($n=4,315$) (because of a failed pass or lost duel) vs. IBPs, where a player was able to pass to a teammate, who was able to retain possession ($n=41,017$). Data shows that IBPs with possession retained show a significantly higher Receiver Availability ($n=41,017$), compared to non-successful IBPs ($n=4,315$, $T=2,707.6$, $p<.05$, $d=0.14$). Besides, comparing with failed pass ($AV=.63$) and lost duels ($AV=.54$), successful pass ($AV=.84$) was finished within higher player AV.

Analysis of Turnovers indicates that Turnovers, in which teams were able to establish ball possession, had a greater number of Players Available compared to Turnovers, when a team loses the ball immediately (Figure 3c). Analysis of successful turnovers ($n=1,579$), in terms of keeping ball possession, shows that the number of

Player Available is associated with higher space gain distances toward the opponent's goal (Figure 3d). On average, teams achieved a longitudinal space gain of 9.08 m within 5s following a turnover.

Post-hoc Mann-Whitney U tests showed numerous significant pairwise differences, particularly between groups with larger differences in Players Available (e.g., 0 vs. 4; 0 vs. ≥ 5), with medium to large effect sizes (r up to .65). For example, mean space gain after 5 seconds was 5.9 m when only one teammate was available, compared to 10.9 m when three teammates were available ($p < .05$, $r = .3$).

Figure 3. Relation of Availability and success. Rate of successful passes (Possession Retained) increased with Receiver Availability (a). Also, IBPs that ended with a successful pass were characterized by significantly higher Receiver Availability compared to those where possession was lost (b). In turnover situations, the number of Players Available is associated with a higher rate of established ball possession (c). Teams with more high-availability players ($AV > 0.8$) achieve significantly greater longitudinal progress toward the opponent's goal (d).

Question iii: Application Scenarios for Availability in Performance Analysis

Figure 4a illustrates the temporal evolution of Players Available following a selected turnover at the team level. Immediately after ball recovery, the number of Players Available (AV threshold $> .8$) increased from 0, over 1 to 2 during the first 3 seconds.

Figure 4b compares the Players Available between two teams across three matches after turnover. It shows that Players Available increases across all three time points after the turnover. This pattern reflects the typical initial spatial expansion of the attacking

team immediately after possession regain. The main difference between the teams is that team B has less Players Available in the seconds immediately following possession gain. For example, there were 7 situations where no player was available 3 seconds after turnover, which increases the chance of losing ball possession again.

At player level, Figure 4c shows a ‘risk-frequency’ profile of one selected player. In general, he passes to receivers with very high availability (.9-1.0), indicating a preference for low-risk passing. The percentile curve further shows that for most lower-availability groups, the players’ pass frequency lies below the population median, indicating that he selects safer passing options more often than most players.

Figure 4d depicts the ‘risk-success’ profile, showing how possession retention rate varies with Receiver Availability. The probability of maintaining possession decreased sharply when Receiver Availability dropped below .4, whereas passes made to receivers with $AV > .6$ had a considerably higher success rate. The percentile curve further shows that this specific player has a better success rate in risky passes compared to the population median.

Figure 4. Application scenarios for Availability in match analysis. Part a) illustrates a typical Turnover situation, in which the Number of Players Available increases in the first 3 seconds after the Turnover (a) from 0, to 1 to 2 players. Based on this, Part b) shows a team Availability profile, that’s aggregates Players Availablely after Turnovers over a set of matches. For both teams, Players Availablely increase by time, which can be attributed to spatial expansion by off-ball movements. The main difference between the teams is that team B has less Players Available in the seconds immediately following

possession gain (b), which might be used as a hint for training. The individual profiles show that the player prefers more low-risk passes (c), high-risky where more successful compared to the mean (d).

Discussion

This study investigated Availability, a metric derived from spatiotemporal tracking data, across three dimensions: face validity, relation to success and practical usefulness for decision-making. Using data from professional soccer matches, we examined how Availability varies under different tactical configurations and spatial contexts.

Firstly, we reported the prevalence of Availability in professional matches (Question i) as a test of the face validity of our implementation (Hughes et al., 2002; O'Donoghue, 2009). In line with conventional wisdom, the metric Players Availability declined under forward-only constraints, reflecting the increased defensive attention on advanced players who are prioritized to prevent space gain (Low et al., 2021). The decline in Players Availability with higher thresholds is mechanically trivial, as stricter criteria naturally reduce the number of available players. The same is trivially true when using the “End” condition compared to “Max” condition, since the time horizon is reduced. Together, these patterns align with the expected behavior of the indicator, supporting its measurement reliability.

Beyond measurement reliability, we next examined the spatial distribution of Availability across the pitch. Availability decreased in central areas and near the opponent's goal, reflecting the tighter defensive pressure (Herold et al., 2022). This likely reflects the defending team's primary objective: restricting progression in a short way towards the goal. Under such pressure, attackers may be forced to use wide areas where passing options are safer. Previous research supports this interpretation: FIFA Training Centre (2025) highlights that attacking teams tend to initiate shots or crosses from wider zones when facing compact defensive structures.

In addition, Player Availability was notably lower in the forward 45° zone ahead of the passer, likely due to the higher concentration of defenders along the most direct path to the goal. This finding aligns with the expectation that central, forward-oriented passing lanes are more heavily contested, as opponents prioritize blocking direct progression toward their own goal. This is supported by evidence that compactness in areas close to the ball is crucial for defensive success (Leander Forcher et al., 2023). Lateral and backward spaces offer more available teammates for ball circulation. Furthermore, Availability decreased with increasing passing distance, which can be attributed to the greater number of interception opportunities and the higher precision required for longer passes. Overall, these spatial variations in Availability reflect how space becomes more constrained under higher defensive pressure.

We next examined whether Availability is associated with passing success and success in turnovers indicated by two sub-aims a) keeping the ball and b) progression (Question ii). Data from both pass-level and IBP-level analyses consistently show a positive relationship, which is evidenced in two ways. First, the rate of successful passes increased monotonically with Receiver Availability. Second, IBPs that ended with a successful pass were characterized by significantly higher Receiver Availability

compared to those where possession was lost. These findings indicate that successful passing depends critically on the Availability of potential receivers. Interestingly, when players lost the ball in a duel, Availability was lower compared to situations where a pass was attempted. Although our data did not include successful take-on, this suggests that players may resort to take-on precisely when teammates are unavailable that a pattern consistent with the risk-reward trade-off documented in passing decision research (Goes et al., 2022).

Decision-making during turnover has been shown to be particularly critical, as effective space utilization in these moments strongly influences team success (Ogawa, Umemoto, & Fujii, 2026). Our data shows that higher Availability facilitates both keeping possession and advancing toward the opponent's goal after turnover situations. Players who won the ball were more likely to maintain possession for their own team after the initial individual possession phase when Availability was higher. Moreover, greater Availability enabled a more vertical and dynamic attacking style. This aligns with previous work emphasizing penetrative passes and spatial penetration for breaking defensive lines (Armatas, 2024; Fernández & Bornn, 2018; Steiner et al., 2018). While higher Availability enables offensive benefits, it may also introduce trade-offs. Research suggested that offensive expansiveness may create defensive vulnerabilities (Borges et al., 2024). Future research should examine how team shape and player positioning influence Availability in both offensive and defensive transitions.

Beyond statistical validation, this study demonstrates practical applications of the Availability (Question iii). Tracking Player Availability after turnovers provides hints for coaches: for example, consistently zero available players three seconds after ball recovery may signal systemic issues in off-ball movement. Of course, such quantitative hints must be validated by qualitative analysis of video footage. The timestamps generated by Availability algorithms can be imported into match analysis tools and provide a convenient way to query such situations. The insights enable targeted interventions which create player-specific awareness during matches, informing substitution decisions, or designing training drills focused on movements into promising zones after turnovers.

Player profiles further allow coaches to compare individual players' passing preferences and success rates across Availability levels in relation to a norm. This may support tactical decisions about who should attempt riskier or less riskier passes and whose technical skills regarding controlling direction and speed of a pass should be improved. These applications illustrate how Availability can translate analytical findings into actionable coaching strategies.

In summary, this study demonstrates three main findings. First, Availability is systematically influenced by threshold, direction, and temporal attribution methods, supporting its face validity. Second, higher Availability is positively associated with passing success, ball retention, and territorial progression after turnovers, confirming its relevance to performance outcomes. Third, temporal tracking of Availability after turnovers provides quantitative hints for coaching interventions, from in-match awareness to training design, illustrating its practical utility for decision-making. Together, these findings offer a novel approach for advancing our understanding of how

player positioning influences Player Availability. Nevertheless, certain limitations should be acknowledged. Since calculation of Availability only uses center of mass data, body orientation is not considered, which might reduce validity of performance indicators. Also, the analysis did not explicitly include defensive pressure or contextual variables such as match status (Freitas, Volossovitch, & Almeida, 2020) and formation changes (Leon Forcher et al., 2022), which may affect AV values.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the data shows empirical validity of our Availability implementation and the performance indicators derived. Results indicate that performance indicators behave not only in line with common wisdom in soccer but are also associated with success on sub-aim level including possession retained rate in passing, ball loss of the ball carrier, keeping ball possession after turn overs and space gain after turnovers. Applications examples has showed how Availability can be used in practice, e.g. by providing lists of turnovers with poor off-ball movement.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank Hendrik Weber and Sportec Solutions / Deutsche Fussball Liga (DFL) for providing the match data. We also thank Ulf Brefeld and Uwe Dick (both Leuphana Universität Lüneburg, Germany) for working on the implementation of the original Availability Model.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

Funding

Jinying Jiang is funded by the China Scholarship Council. The institution had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or manuscript preparation.

Reference

- Anzer, G., & Bauer, P. (2022). Expected passes. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, 36(1), 295-317. doi:10.1007/s10618-021-00810-3
- Armatas, V. (2024). Predicting offensive sector entry during transition moments in soccer. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part P: Journal of Sports Engineering and Technology*, 1-8. doi:10.1177/17543371241279576
- Baca, A., & Perl, J. (2018). *Modelling and simulation in sport and exercise*. London: Routledge.
- Borges, P. H., Ueda, L. S. C., Souza, P. V. d., Binda, M. E. V., Silva, J. F. d., & Guilherme, J. R. J. (2024). Original actions performed by a beginner attacker modify defensive dispersion in small-sided soccer games. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1), 28489. doi:10.1038/s41598-024-79741-0
- Davis, J., Bransen, L., Devos, L., Jaspers, A., Meert, W., Robberechts, P., . . . Roy, M. V. (2024). Methodology and evaluation in sports analytics: challenges, approaches, and lessons learned. *MACHINE LEARNING*, 113(9), 6977-7010. doi:10.1007/s10994-024-06585-0
- Dick, U., Link, D., & Brefeld, U. (2022). Who can receive the pass? A computational model for quantifying availability in soccer. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, 36, 1-28. doi:10.1007/s10618-022-00827-2
- Fernández, J., & Bornn, L. (2018). *Wide open spaces: A statistical technique for measuring space creation in professional soccer*. Paper presented at the MIT SLOAN SPORTS ANALYTICS CONFERENCE, Boston, MA.
- FIFA Training Centre. (2025). CR Flamengo: Disrupting a defensive block with wide-area rotations. Retrieved from <https://www.fifatrainingcentre.com/en/game/tournaments/fic/2025/cr-flamengo-disrupting-defensive-block-with-wide-area-rotations.php>
- Forcher, L., Forcher, L., Altmann, S., Jekauc, D., & Kempe, M. (2023). Is a compact organization important for defensive success in elite soccer? – Analysis based on player tracking data. *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 19(2), 757-768. doi:10.1177/17479541231172695
- Forcher, L., Forcher, L., Wäsche, H., Jekauc, D., Woll, A., & Altmann, S. (2022). The influence of tactical formation on physical and technical match performance in male soccer: A systematic review. *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 18(5), 1820 - 1849.
- Franks, I., & Hughes, M. (2016). *Soccer Analytics: Successful Coaching Through Match Analysis* Aachen: Meyer & Meyer Sport.
- Freitas, R., Volossovitch, A., & Almeida, C. H. (2020). Associations of situational and performance variables with defensive transitions outcomes in FIFA World Cup 2018. *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 16(1), 131-147. doi:10.1177/1747954120953666
- Goes, F., Kempe, M., Meerhoff, R., & Lemmink, K. A. P. M. (2018). Not Every Pass Can Be an Assist: A Data-Driven Model to Measure Pass Effectiveness in Professional Soccer Matches. *BIG DATA*, 7(1), 57-70.

doi:10.1089/big.2018.0067

- Goes, F., Schwarz, E., Elferink-Gemser, M., Lemmink, K., & Brink, M. (2022). A risk-reward assessment of passing decisions: comparison between positional roles using tracking data from professional men's soccer. *Science and Medicine in Football*, 6(3), 372-380. doi:10.1080/24733938.2021.1944660
- Herold, M., Hecksteden, A., Radke, D., Goes, F., Nopp, S., Meyer, T., & Kempe, M. (2022). Off-ball behavior in association football: A data-driven model to measure changes in individual defensive pressure. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 40(12), 1412-1425. doi:10.1080/02640414.2022.2081405
- Hughes, M., & Bartlett, R. (2002). The use of performance indicators in performance analysis. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 20(10), 739-754. doi:10.1080/026404102320675602
- Hughes, M., & Franks, I. (2005). Analysis of passing sequences, shots and goals in soccer. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 23(5), 509-514. doi:10.1080/02640410410001716779
- Lames, M., & McGarry, T. (2007). On the search for reliable performance indicators in game sports. *International Journal of Performance Analysis in Sport*, 7(1), 62-79. doi:10.1080/24748668.2007.11868388
- Lang, S. (2026). *Spatiotemporal Data Analysis in Soccer Using Machine Learning Approaches*. Technical University of Munich, Munich, Germany.
- Link, D., & Hoernig, M. (2017). Individual ball possession in soccer. *PLoS One*, 12(7), e0179953. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0179953
- Linke, D., Link, D., & Lames, M. (2020). Football-specific validity of TRACAB's optical video tracking systems. *PLoS One*, 15(3), e0230179. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0230179
- Lotte, B., Pieter, R., Haaren, J. V., & Jesse, D. (2019). *Choke or Shine? Quantifying Soccer Players' Abilities to Perform Under Mental Pressure*. Paper presented at the 13th MIT Sloan Sports Analytics Conference, Boston, MA.
- Low, B., Rein, R., Raabe, D., Schwab, S., & Memmert, D. (2021). The porous high-press? An experimental approach investigating tactical behaviours from two pressing strategies in football. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 39(19), 2199-2210. doi:10.1080/02640414.2021.1925424
- Mackenzie, R., & Cushion, C. (2013). Performance analysis in football: A critical review and implications for future research. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 31(6), 639-676. doi:10.1080/02640414.2012.746720
- Memmert, D. (2025). Editorial for Sports Performance section of Journal of Sports Sciences: Moving match analysis forward – Guidelines and perspectives. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 43(18), 1899-1906. doi:10.1080/02640414.2025.2535850
- Memmert, D., & Perl, J. (2009). *Football informatics: A combination of game theory, optimization, machine learning, and statistics*: Springer.
- Morgulev, E., & Lebed, F. (2024). Beyond key performance indicators. *German Journal of Exercise and Sport Research*, 54(3), 335-340. doi:10.1007/s12662-024-00944-8

- O'Donoghue, P. (2009). *Research Methods for Sports Performance Analysis*. London: Routledge.
- Ogawa, Y., Umemoto, R., & Fujii, K. (2026). *Pitch-Wide Space Evaluation for Soccer Transitions*. Paper presented at the Machine Learning and Data Mining for Sports Analytics, Cham.
- Overmeer, T., Janssen, T., & Nuijten, W. P. M. (2025). Revisiting Expected Possession Value in Football: Introducing a U-Net Architecture, Reward and Risk for Passes, and a Benchmark. *arXiv*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2502.02565>
- Pappalardo, L., Cintia, P., Rossi, A., Massucco, E., Ferragina, P., Pedreschi, D., & Giannotti, F. (2019). A public data set of spatio-temporal match events in soccer competitions. *Science Data*, 6(1), 236. doi:10.1038/s41597-019-0247-7
- Power, P., Ruiz, H., Wei, X., & Lucey, P. (2017). *Not all passes are created equal: Objectively measuring the risk and reward of passes in soccer from tracking data*. Paper presented at the In Proceedings of ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, New York, United States.
- Steiner, S., Rauh, S., Rumo, M., Sonderegger, K., & Seiler, R. (2018). Using position data to estimate effects of perceptual features of play on passing decisions in soccer. *Current Issues in Sport Science*, 3, 1-9.
- Stöckl, M., Lamb, P. F., & Lames, M. (2012). A Model for Visualizing Difficulty in Golf and Subsequent Performance Rankings on the PGA Tour. *International Journal of Golf Science*, 1(1), 10-24. doi:doi: 10.1123/ijgs.1.1.10